

SOME IMPORTANT ASPECTS OF COMMUNICATIVE VOCABULARY

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6946161>

Jakbarov Musokhon Pulotovich

A teacher of the Uzbekistan State World languages University

Annotation: *This article discusses about vocabulary, its usage in writing, reading, listening and speaking skills. Vocabulary is important because it's the basis of all languages. It's the raw building blocks that we can use to express our thoughts and ideas, share information, understand others and grow personal relationships.*

Key words: *Communicative Vocabulary, basic meaning, preferred context, associations, appropriate, native and non-native speaker, flexibility, reading comprehension, language development, occupational success, personal relationships, language and literacy skills.*

Every word in a language comes with multiple layers of information. Among them include its: ***Basic meaning(s); *Preferred contexts/common occurrences; *Associations.** The first two criteria are what is commonly taught in vocabulary lessons in classrooms. The third criterion is what creates the richness in native speakers' knowledge of words. Associations give plenty of meaning and flexibility to a word and are the reason why it can be challenging to teach puns to non-native speakers. The communicative vocabulary module is taught for the purpose of to enlarge the range of students' vocabulary, to develop students' ability to recognize and use words in communication, as well as, to enhance students' use of appropriate strategies for building and storing vocabulary.

Students' communication abilities, including their vocabulary, can vary immensely. Here are the top 5 reasons why vocabulary is so important.

1. **It improves Reading Comprehension.** Research has shown that kids need to understand 98% of the words they read to understand what they are reading. Improving vocabulary skills will improve their understanding of novels and textbooks.
2. **It's important to Language Development.** Children who develop a rich vocabulary tend to be deeper thinkers, express themselves better and read more. Improving language and literacy skills early in life will help them be more successful academically and communicatively.
3. **Communicating ideas.** Successful communication or "saying what you mean" is dependent upon a good vocabulary base. Using the right words when talking, makes you a more effective communicator.
4. **Expressing Yourself in Writing.** Having a good vocabulary to draw from can help you write more effectively. Students need to use a more formal tone when writing – not conversational language – and to do that, they need a richer vocabulary to tap into those words we don't use when we speak.

5. **Occupational Success.** Researcher Johnson O'Connor found that “a person’s vocabulary level is the best single predictor of occupational success”.
*Success in the business place depends on your communication skills.

When it comes to learning a foreign language such as English, many students spend hours working through textbooks, doing grammar exercises and perhaps even watching the occasional Netflix show in their target language. However, many people don’t realize that working on vocabulary is just as important, if not more important when it comes to success in learning a foreign language.

Students studying at higher educational establishments are taught on the following course objective in communicative vocabulary aspect:

- Recognize word meaning in the context of topics students are familiar with (description of events, feelings, ambitions, dreams, wishes, etc.)
- Identify appropriate uses of words, phrases in topics familiar to students, of personal interest or relevant to everyday life (family, hobbies, work, travel, etc.)
- Recognize and use stress patterns of words relevant to the topic of students
- Recognize and apply a range of strategies for guessing, storing and learning vocabulary
- Make appropriate use of resources (e.g. paper, electronic and on – line dictionaries etc.) to build students’ vocabulary
- Identify the differences between active and passive vocabulary for students’ own needs.

Students already know thousands of words, and they will continue to learn more whether they work at it or not. The fact is that many of the words they know were probably learned simply by coming across them often enough in their reading, in conversation, and even while watching television. But increasing the number of learning requires a consistent, dedicated approach. If a student learned only one new word a day for the next three years, he/she would have over a thousand new words in your vocabulary. However, if a learner decided right now to learn ten new words a day, in one year he would have added over three thousand to what he already know, and probably have established a lifetime habit of learning and self – studying.

The steps we discuss do not involve the use of vocabulary – building aids such as books, tapes, or CDs; all that is required is a dictionary. But what about such materials? Are they worth using? We say yes.

The first advantage of vocabulary – building books is that they present you with words generally considered important to know, thus saving you time. Another advantage of many of these books is that they will use the words in several sentences, so that you can see the words in different contexts. A third advantage is that they usually have exercises that test what students have learned, which gives them a clear sense of progress. Four basic steps are considered to a better vocabulary. While there are not any magic shortcuts to learning words, the larger your vocabulary becomes, the easier it will be to connect a new word with words they already know, and thus remember its meaning. So, learning speed should increase as your vocabulary grows.

There are four basic steps to building your vocabulary: Be aware of words. Read. Use a dictionary. Most people know how to use a dictionary to look up a word's meaning. Here are some pointers on how to do this as a part of a vocabulary – building program:

- Have your own dictionary. Keep it where you usually do your reading at home. You are more likely to use it if you do not have to get it from another room. At work, there may be a good dictionary available for your use. At home, most people do not have a big, unabridged dictionary; however, one of the smaller collegiate dictionaries would be fine to start with.

- Circle the words you look up. After you have done this for a while, your eye will naturally move to the words you have circled whenever you flip through the dictionary. This will give you a quick form of review.

- Read the entire entry for the word you look up. Remember, words can have more than one meaning, and the meaning you need for the word you are looking up may not be the first one given in your dictionary. Even if it is, the other meanings of the word will help you understand the different ways the word is used.

- Study and Review Regularly.

Also, the word's history, usually given near the beginning of the entry, can often give a fascinating picture of the way the word has developed its current meaning. This will add to the pleasure of learning the word as well as help you remember it. In a nutshell, I would like to say that vocabulary is important because it's the basis of all languages. It's the raw building blocks that we can use to express our thoughts and ideas, share information, understand others and grow personal relationships.

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